

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE IX

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

September 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

@pinagpalapublishingservices	<input type="button" value="Search"/>
pinagpala_publishing	<input type="button" value="Search"/>
www.pinagpalapublishing.com	<input type="button" value="Search"/>

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.121-135, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

LGBT Characters in Philippine Indie Films: Towards Discovering The Filipino Rainbow Psyche

Dr. Carlito C. Biales
Dr. Ma. Antoinette C. Montealegre

Philippine Normal University , Manila

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to discover the aspects/features that would make up the Filipino Rainbow Psyche using Lyotard's Plurality of Judgments, Žižek's Ideology, and Ruby Rich's Queer Cinema. This research attempted to capture the human experience and social life of the LGBT++ as depicted in selected independent films in the hope of defining the aspects/features that reveal their psyche. In this context, the aspects of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche were observed and identified using the following indicators: individual rights, liberty, image, and gaze, and positive self-identification as the bases for the analysis and discussion. It was found that generally LGBT gazes are somewhat attractive to other LGBT++ viewers who desire to be accepted as normal people, especially by their family. The LGBT++ characters studied enjoy their individual rights and freedom that mirror their psyche. The aspects/features of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche identified include: 1) freedom to express their true identity and to be true to oneself; 2) freedom to love without fear of rejection, ridicule or disapproval; 3) ability to fight manipulation and failure; 4) desire to live without prejudice and enjoy a non-conformist relationship; 5) desire to live in an amoral society; 6) aspiration to be an Overman (Nietzschean in a limited sense); 7) desire to achieve 'the other' consciousness; and 8) a yearning to find another kindred spirit who touches the depths of their soul.

Introduction

In recent years, LGBT themes have been conspicuous in Philippine cinema, and these might have paved the way for the emergence of a homosexual culture in the different sectors of society. The themes depict LGBTs in a positive light, i.e., as professionals, as achievers, as career-oriented people, among others. The LGBTs are presented in recent indie films as elite or from the middle class, as yuppies (young urban professionals), and even educated professionals in the academe and competent CEOs or directors in the corporate world. Altman (2001) claims that beginning in the mid-1990s in Metro Manila and the Southeast Asian region, images of muscled gay men images became fashionable. However, independent films are not usually shown in famous theaters in the country, but rather released during film festivals where indie filmmakers and film aficionados can showcase their films. Some of these popular film festivals are the Cinemalaya Film Festival,

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

CineFilipino Film Festival, QCinema Film Festival, and Cinema One Originals Film Festival. Moreover, independent or indie films are usually designed for short films, documentaries, experimental films, and even animation films, which are produced with a small capital or budget (Primer.com.ph). Since they are low-budget productions, they are most likely financed or funded by either public or private organizations. From the 90's onwards, the number of LGBT representations in local films and TV shows noticeably grew. LGBT representations have widened their scope from independent to mainstream and into the main broadsheet media.

experiences of lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transgender women and men.

Moreover, LGBT films have positively portrayed characters to disengage the distorted images of LGBT individuals who are still treated differently, either as ostracized people or a bane of society. In terms of their depiction, LGBT characters have always been associated with controversies (most LGBT films, either local or international, are highly controversial because of their sexual content) that trigger highly politicized reviews or negative comments and even earn the condemnation of some religious groups. Moreover, LGBT films attempt to project a positive image of LGBT individuals to mainstream audiences. Locally, this positive image has been seen in some Filipino LGBT films. For instance, Lana's *Die Beautiful* of 2016 is about a transgender woman whose dream is to become a beauty queen. Likewise, the TV series *Destiny Rose* is about a transgender woman who wishes to be accepted as a woman. These local films and television shows focus on LGBT characters searching for true love and happiness while struggling for familial and social acceptance.

Given the above discussion and perspective on LGBT portrayal in films, the present study looked into the psychological perspectives of LGBT characters in Philippine indie films to discover the psyche of LGBT characters, which this study will call the **Filipino Rainbow Psyche**. Further, this study explored the LGBT psychology which Manalastas and Torre (2016) in their research study mentioned that "the Philippine case is no exception where same-sex marriage, gender identity recognition, sex work, abortion, and even heterosexual divorce remain illegal and it shows to be an unlikely environment for affirmation, fostering inclusion, and activism for gender and sexual minorities within psychology". Moreover, the studies of Clarke and Braun (2006) and Rich (2013) explored about LGBT psychology that provided a "resource for thinking new subject-positions associated with different sexualities, and as such, was important in contributing to an emergent identity-politics around LGBT sexualities."

Further, the researcher utilized the theories of Lyotard's Multiplicity of Judgments, Žižek's Theory of Ideology, and Rich's New Queer Cinema together with the use of psychology to determine the aspects/features of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche of the lead characters in the LGBT indie films in the Philippine context. Moreover, five indicators - individual rights, liberty, image, gaze, and positive self-depiction - were used to analyze the LGBT characters in lead roles through the lens of philosophy and psychology.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

This study aimed to delve into a body of knowledge that has not been explored extensively to create new spaces in the field of LGBT psychology as represented in literature. Most significantly, the term Filipino Rainbow Psyche has never been coined or used by any researcher. The researcher postulates that the discovery of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche of Filipino LGBT characters from the present study offered an avenue to significantly understand LGBT individuals on why they have different preferences, values, and beliefs. Through this study, the “psyche” of an LGBT individual may be better understood via the literary tools used to unearth it.

Research Problems

The following research problems guided the researcher in analyzing the LGBT characters in selected Philippine indie films to discover the aspects/features that constitute the Filipino Rainbow Psyche.

1. How are the LGBT characters in lead roles in the selected Philippine indie films portrayed based on the following indicators/constructs:
Individual rights and liberty (Lyotard's Multiplicity (Plurality) of Judgments)
Image and gaze (Žižek's Theory of Ideology)
Positive self-identification (Rich's New Queer Cinema)?
2. What are the discovered aspects/features of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche as gleaned from the analysis of the LGBT characters in the selected films studied?

Methodology

Arts-based qualitative Research and Methodology

Eisner coined the term “arts-based research” (ABR) in the early 1990s and developed it into a major methodological genre. However, larger shifts occurring in prior decades set the stage for ABR. Specifically, Leavy (2015) used it in the development of creative arts therapies, advances in the study of arts and learning (especially in neuroscience), and developments in qualitative research have all influenced the emergence of ABR in many recent studies.

Results and Discussion

In the films studied, Filipino LGBT behavior is depicted as consistent with their identity. Johnson (1973) defines identity as “what you can say you are according to what they say you can be” (p. 58). It was noted that the lesbian characters portray more ability to express their beliefs, thoughts, ideas, and emotions without being hindered by any existing norms or standards compared to gay, bisexual, and transgender individuals. It is likewise important to note that they are also presented as LGBT individuals who enjoy their freedom, have gained social acceptance, and have achieved a degree of self-esteem

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

which appears to be a strong positive self-identification. Moreover, the Filipino Rainbow Psyche portrayed by the lesbian characters relates to the way they handle external judgment from their family, friends, or professional circles, as they aspire for a genderless world and an amoral society where true love is the binding element. They also long to find another person of the same gender who could understand their desire to love and to be loved. The lesbian characters in the films do not care about other people's opinions; what is important is that they stay true to themselves. For them, their self-worth and authenticity give them freedom to live a purpose-driven existence. They do not want to be trapped by any fear of external judgment or live within its restricted walls. The lesbian psyche illustrates a pervasive drive to continue positive and significant interpersonal relationships for themselves and for the people around them.

Moreover, the Filipino Rainbow Psyche shows an LGBT individual enjoying full acceptance amidst the intolerance, discrimination, and homophobia from different sectors in society. One aspect/feature of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche discovered from the films studied reveals that the LGBT individuals have the desire to be accepted like any other human being, especially by their family. Social acceptance permits them to enjoy their gender orientation. Their happiness comes from their ability to freely express their feelings as they search for the greater purpose of their existence. It is necessary to note that the gay character is depicted as a strong-willed individual who has a strong desire for social justice and his rights as he strives to achieve self-worth and authenticity. However, some films also present a darker side of gays' willingness to engage in unethical behavior and to rebel against norms and family. This creates the idea that the gay psyche wants to exercise freedom regardless of whether someone else is harmed or disobeyed. The gay character is portrayed as someone who can face people's judgment without fear of social condemnation. From a Nietzschean perspective, the gay character exhibits the traits of an "Overman" in a limited sense.

Another feature of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche is the fear of being judged and ostracized by people around them, being scared to come out, especially to their own family, because of their gender orientation/preference. It seems so difficult for them to come out, and their sense of right and wrong seems to be dictated by external forces. This feature is especially found in the bisexual characters who are depicted as selfish and insecure in the face of infidelity. They are portrayed as possessive partners needing reassurance to feel secure in a relationship. The bisexual image is conflicted since they portray differing degrees of gender identity establishment, and there is a need to blur the gender lines. The films suggest that bisexual individuals are always confused as to whom he or she should love, a male or a female. The films also portray a negative aspect of being bisexual because he/she is either being romantically betrayed or pictured as the unfaithful one.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Table 10 Shows the overall summary of the discovered Filipino Rainbow Psyche
General Summary of the Rainbow Psyche

Constructs/Indicators		Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
Forever (2016): Valdez.	Natin Cyrus	The characters have accepted their identities without reservation. They can freely express their romantic love without fear of defying any social conventions or moral judgment. Their rights and freedom are exercised without restriction or inhibition.	Their image is depicted as successful individuals who pursue their personal and professional growth. They are portrayed as free from the judgmental gaze of other people. They are attractive to other lesbians	The lesbian characters are well-accepted, and their social roles are recognized and appreciated.	The lesbian characters have both strong relationships through binding contracts. The binding contract is used to show a unique Filipino feature in a lesbian relationship. They have the freedom to express their true identity and true to themselves.
Baka (2016): Lee	Bukas Samantha	A lesbian is someone who can choose for herself what is right and proper. She enjoys a sense of freedom, and there are no	It depicts a lesbian relationship as a beautiful, tender bond between two people who deserve	Character's portrayal needs to recognize that being true to oneself and her behavior is a part of	The lesbian character is afraid to come out, and it can be said that this aspect is part of her fear of social judgment,

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
	limitations in terms of individual rights and freedom.	to love and to be loved openly. The gaze appears to be attractive to fellow millennials and lesbians who are torn between being true to their own identities.	positive self-identification . Her real self applies to her personal experiences and is primarily positive, as she tends to feel good about how she sees herself and the world as a positive and safe place.	which becomes an imagined self-limiting obstacle for herself.
Muli (2010): Adolfo Alix	The character feels no constraints limiting him when it comes to the expression of his gay romantic interest and does not pose any obstacle at all in terms of choices and actions towards Errol.	His image sets as an ideal preference that does not hinder being successful or achieving self-actualization- the process of becoming what one is	His character shows apparent self-expression of his gender identity and a healthy sense of self-worth or positive self-identification . He remains true and believes in	The gay self-expression is unhampered by prevailing social forces, and there are no apparent obstacles to the character's free expression as he engages in an open relationship (having two

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
		capable of becoming. His gaze is inviting to the homosexual s who want to be recognized and respected as successful people in society, and not to be seen merely as gays who are judged because of their gender.	himself, who deserves to live a life without suppression and restrictions. He also displays in a limited sense the attribute of an "Overman" who has his own value, independent of others, self-determined, shows mastery and self-confidence, and is free of concern for the judgment of others. But cannot be a full Overman because he has no lofty goal to change the	romantic relationships at the same time).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
			world, except perhaps when he pursues his political activism.	
Ang Pagdadalaga ni Maximo Oliveros (2005):Auratus Solito	The character appears that everything is acceptable, and no one passes judgment in the name of morality, and this is his freedom. His right and freedom to decide for himself and choose to do what he wants show that he is freely evaluating, analyzing, and judging different values and issues, but not according to global fixed criteria. His innocence is freedom itself.	His image is portrayed as a dutiful son and sibling. He appears to be a very responsible and disciplined individual at his young age. His gaze is likable to a parent viewer who values an obedient, caring, and responsible child. His character is also pleasing to the gaze of effeminate	The character portrayed in a socially attractive way and having a strong positive self-identification without any insecurities is depicted in the film. His identity is an act of identification that aims to eradicate prejudice and instill pride.	The young gay psyche is portrayed as accepted by society, responsible, and kind to others. He is carefree and seeks only to follow the desires of his heart. The long-term consequences of decisions are not considered or are perhaps denied and ignored. But most importantly, his being innocent

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
Ang Lalake sa Parola (2007): Joselito Altarejo	The character cannot be said that he enjoys complete rights and liberties, which refers to the reduction already by itself, as the expression of the freedom of the pure ego. This expression of freedom is reflected in the personality of the character as he is confronted by social forces. Perhaps his ego is not a consciousness conceived of logically, but an actual consciousness.	gays at his age.	Positive self-identification is ostensibly lacking because of the struggles of the bisexual character. It also shows the absence of acceptance for himself and understanding who is, and learning to accept himself as a bisexual.	is a freedom in itself.
		The character's image represents his ideal ego, which stands for the idealized self-image of the subject because the bisexual side is still struggling with the decision to acknowledge that identity. His gaze is pleasing to individuals who are faced with the same gender confusion and similar romantic struggles		

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
		that may be met with social resistance from their own family or community.		
Changing Partners (2017): Dan Villegas	Individual rights and liberty are demonstrated in all four relationships. They chose to set aside the potential reactions of the public about their age gaps and regard these reactions as mere opinions that are not absolute standards of right and wrong. They are free to decide on a course of action based on the consequences they perceive would be	Due to the flawed personalities of the characters, certain aspects of these characters are the ideal ego image. A viewer who wants to be a dominant, responsible, and successful professional (Alex). A viewer who wishes to be cared for, pampered, dependent,	They are portrayed in the film as exhibiting positive self-identification because of the apparent absence of any form of ridicule or discrimination towards them by other people.	The bisexual characters' psyche illustrates a strong absence of fear of negative social norms/standards or criteria, and obviously, domination in the relationship with his/her partner is one thing that features in a Filipino bisexual relationship. They also demonstrate the freedom to love without

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche	
	engendered. The bisexual relationships illustrated an apparent absence of fear of negative social reactions	and relatively free (Cris) as an ideal ego. The gaze of younger Crises, viewed by those who desire to be dominated and cared for by them, on the other hand, those viewers who are directed to the older, successful, and more mature Alexes of the world		fear or rejection.	
Quick Change (2013)	Eduardo Roy, Jr.	The character reveals herself the idea of what is right and wrong is relative and subjective. Doing malpractice and illegal by law, sees it as a way of	The image is reflected on acceptance, and the gaze is attractive to those transgender individuals	The character shows a positive self-identification through her positive attitude in facing all	The transgender's psyche demonstrates her ability to fulfill her own happiness by her own standards, as

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.93-120, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Constructs/Indicators	Using Lyotard's theory of plurality/multiplicity of judgment (Individual rights and liberty)	Using Zizek's ideology (image and gaze).	Using Ruby Rich's Queer (positive self-identification).	Filipino Rainbow Psyche
	helping her own kind achieve happiness and fulfillment by her own standards. She also illustrated her rights and freedom when she rejected the idea of her boyfriend to have a full sex-change operation.	who themselves have received acceptance.	odds and in accepting her reality. Being transgender is malleable and fluid, construed by her self-views, experiences, and contexts over her choice as a transgender.	the character is not afraid to engage in illegal underground collagen enhancement for her clients.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the above findings, the following major conclusions are drawn:

1. The LGBT characters in the films studied show the desire to enjoy their individual rights and freedom. They need the freedom to express their true identity and to be true to themselves; the freedom to love without fear of rejection, ridicule or disapproval; the ability to fight manipulation and failure; the desire to live without prejudice and enjoy a non-conformist relationship; the freedom to live in an amoral society; to be an Overman in a limited sense; to achieve “the other” consciousness; and to find another kindred spirit who touches the depths of their soul. However, except for the protagonist in *Ang Lalake sa Parola*, who experiences a bisexual dilemma, the other LGBT protagonists show a willingness to engage in unethical behavior, rebel against the norms and family, and be independent of others.
2. Most LGBT images and gazes are reflected in their personal and professional growth. Their gazes are somewhat attractive to other LGBT viewers who desire to be accepted, especially by their family, to live with pride, and to redefine and blur lines across all genders.
3. The LGBT characters from *Forever Natin*, *Baka Bukas, Muli*, and *Ang Pagdadalaga ni Maximo Oliveros* portray a healthy degree of self-esteem, social acceptance, self-worth, and authenticity. They desire to live a purpose-driven existence and show a strong positive self-identification among LGBT individuals. In contrast, in the films *Changing Partners*, *Ang Lalake sa Parola*, *Quick Change*, and *Die Beautiful*, the protagonists portray a limited positive self-identification.
4. The LGBT characters from the selected films studied portrayed some unique features based on the Filipino Rainbow Psyche, such as that innocence is a freedom itself, being afraid to come out, no fear to engage in illegal activity, open relationship, strong relationship through binding contract, the tendency to dominate over their partners, and resiliency.
5. Given the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for future researchers and curriculum planners.

Recommendations

1. Researchers may use other theories/literary approaches aside from those of Lyotard, Žižek, and Ruby Rich to validate the existence of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche, as shown in the present study.
2. Other sources of materials may be used aside from LGBT Filipino indie films to elaborate/discover/interpret further the aspects/features of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche and provide comprehensive results, e.g., Filipino soap operas/’teleserye’ or contemporary short stories and novels.
3. Future researchers may use more Filipino LGBT indie films to confirm the potential plausibility of the Filipino Rainbow Psyche among LGBT character portrayals.

References:

- Altman, D. (2001). *Global sex*. University of Chicago Press.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), Article 2.
- Johnston, J. (1973). *Lesbian nation: The feminist solution*. Simon and Schuster.
- Leavy, P. (2015). *Method meets art: Arts-based research practice* (2nd ed.). The Guilford Press.
- Langellier, K. M., & Peterson, E. E. (2006). Shifting contexts in personal narrative performance. In D. Madison & J. Hamera, *The SAGE Handbook of Performance Studies* (pp. 151–168). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412976145.n9>
- Liotard, J.-F. (1984). *The postmodern condition: A report on knowledge*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Liotard, J.-F. (1985). *Just gaming: Theory and history of literature*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Liotard, J.-F. (1993). *Toward the Postmodern* (R. Harvey, Ed.; 1. publ). Humanities Press.
- Liotard, J.-F. (1996). *The inhuman: Reflections on time* (Repr.). Stanford Univ. Press.
- Liotard, J.-F. (2002). *Discourse, figure*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Liotard, J.-F. (2007). *The differend: Phrases in dispute* (7th printing). University of Minnesota Press.
- Liotard, J.-F., & Lyotard, J.-F. (2005). *The postmodern condition: A report on knowledge* (Repr.). Manchester Univ. Pr.
- Manalastas, E. J., & Torre, B. A. (2016). LGBT psychology in the Philippines. *Psychology of Sexualities Review*, 7(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.53841/bpssex.2016.7.1.60>
- Rich, B. R. (2013). *New queer cinema: The director's cut*. Duke University Press.
- Shelburne, W. A. (1976). *C.G. Jung's theory of the collective unconscious: A rational reconstruction* [Published Dissertation]. University of Florida.
- Worthen, W. B. (1998). Drama, performativity, and performance. *PMLA/Publications of the Modern Language Association of America*, 113(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.2307/463244>
- Žižek, S. (1989). *The sublime object of ideology*. Verso.
- Žižek, S. (1992). *Looking awry: An introduction to Jacques Lacan through popular culture*. MIT Press.
- Žižek, S. (1994). *Tarrying with the negative: Kant, Hegel and the critique of ideology* (2 print). Duke Univ. Press.
- Žižek, S. (2001). *The Metastases of enjoyment: Six essays on women and causality* (Reprint). Verso.
- Žižek, S. (Ed.). (2003). *Jacques Lacan: Critical evaluations in cultural theory*. Routledge.
- Žižek, S. (2008). *The sublime object of ideology*. Verso.
- Žižek, S. (2009). *In defense of lost causes*. Verso.
- Žižek, S. (2013). *Less than nothing: Hegel and the shadow of dialectical materialism* (Paperback ed). Verso.
- Žižek, S., & Žižek, S. (2008). *The plague of fantasies* (New ed.). Verso.
- Zubiri-Esnaola, H., Vidu, A., Rios-Gonzalez, O., & Morla-Folch, T. (2020). Inclusivity, participation, and collaboration: Learning in interactive groups. *Educational Research*, 62(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2020.1755605>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17158794